

1 **Arhgap28 functions in lineage commitment in the human embryo.**

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7 We measured total transcription in the inner cell mass (ICM) and the trophectoderm (TE) of the human
8 embryo to understand the mechanisms underlying TE commitment. We describe here discovery of
9 Arhgap28 as a lineage commitment factor or lineage commitment cooperating factor in embryonic stem
10 cells of the human embryo.

11 Citations

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